

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF CFRP TO PERFORATED STEEL JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

The elastic properties mismatch between CFRP and steel makes joining them difficult. One way to reduce this mismatch is to gradually decrease the average stiffness of the steel part of the joint by perforating it. The present study investigates flat co-infused perforated steel to CFRP joint configurations that offer a transitional zone of stiffness in the joint site. Further, the possible advantage of mechanical interlocking is investigated. The steel parts are perforated with circular holes. The hole diameters are smaller near the edge of the composite, and increase with increasing depth in to the composite skins of the joint, thus creating a graded steel component. The steel part is joined to the composite by inserting it between CFRP skins. In total, five flat joint configurations are proposed for static tensile testing. These are a non-perforated joint configuration (reference) and two different patterns of perforated joint configurations. The two different perforation patterns are tested with and without PTFE material in the holes, allowing adhesive material (resin) in the holes to assess the hypothesis of mechanical interlocking. Finite element analyses are used to elucidate the experimental results. Perforated steel joints showed a 175% increase of joint strength comparing to non-perforated ones.

1 INTRODUCTION

Joining of composites parts, together with their damage tolerance and inserts, are of paramount importance in mechanical design because they cause structural discontinuities that are often the Achilles heel of a structural design. Joining composite with metal parts leads, inevitably, to high stress concentrations due to the material property mismatch. Since such joints are used in high performance structures, a new approach is needed to meet this challenge. This paper is inspired by the biomimetics approach, where nature uses a transitional zone of stiffness in the insertion site when joining dissimilar materials [1].

One way to apply this design to engineering joints is to gradually decrease the stiffness of the joint metal part by perforating it. In this paper, co-infused carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) to perforated steel joints were numerically and experimentally investigated under static mechanical testing.

2 CONFIGURATIONS INVESTIGATED

The configurations proposed and analysed consisted of co-infused joints made of unidirectional CFRP and perforated steel plates (Fig. 1). For comparison, reference specimens (Test 1) were tested with the exact same configuration but with a non-perforated steel part. The steel part was perforated to create a transitional zone of stiffness between the steel and CFRP adherends [2-4]. The perforation patterns consist of two different configurations where the diameter of the largest set of holes nearest to the end of the steel part was 4 mm for small hole (SH; Test 2) and 5 mm for large hole (LH; Test 3) specimens (Fig. 2), respectively, decreasing in diameter by 0.25 mm with each row (for a total of seven rows).

Both perforated configurations were tested with and without PTFE material in the holes to investigate if the perforations increased the joint strength by mechanical interlocking associated with

ingress of resin and/or fibres into the holes (Tests 4 and 5). The purpose of the joint configurations with PTFE material in the holes is to restrict the bond/access of the resin and fibres in the holes.

The only difference between the two perforated configurations is the hole diameters in the steel plates (Figs. 2 and 3). All the other geometric variables remained the same.

Figure 1: Co-infused CFRP to perforated steel joint.

Figure 2: Small Hole (SH) and Large Hole (LH) steel perforation patterns, dimensions in mm.

3 FINITE ELEMENT INVESTIGATION

Three-dimensional finite-element models of perforated steel to CFRP joints were developed with the finite element software ABAQUS® 6.12. A three-dimensional model was required to study the joint behaviour due to the three dimensional stress state introduced by the complicated geometry of the perforation patterns. To accurately calculate the load carrying capacity of the adhesive joints, cohesive elements were used for the simulation, under the framework of Cohesive Zone Modeling (CZM) techniques [5, 6]. The mesh density was chosen as the best compromise between convergence, accuracy and computational cost. The adhesive layer was modelled with a single layer of cohesive elements [7].

Figure 3: Perforated steel used for (a) Test 2 (SH) samples and (b) Test 3 (LH) samples.

In the present analysis, the triangular CZM degradation formulation was chosen because of its simplicity, widespread use for investigation purposes, especially for brittle adhesives [7], and availability in ABAQUS[®]. An adhesive thickness of 0.2 mm was used for the numerical modeling. The dimensions of the adherends and the Overlap Length (OL) can be seen in Figure 4. A geometrically non-linear static analysis was performed, modelling the CFRP and steel adherends with elastic orthotropic and isotropic material properties, respectively. Fixed boundary conditions were applied to the CFRP end of the joint to reproduce the testing machine gripping. A displacement u_x was applied to the steel end of the model together with a lateral restraint (Fig. 5).

Figure 4: Side view of the joint (dimensions in mm).

Figure 5: Loading and boundary conditions.

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

4.1 Specimen manufacture

Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) was used to co-bond the CFRP to the steel plate. Both parts of the mould were designed and manufactured for the purpose of this study. The mould consisted of one resin inlet and two vacuum outlets (Fig. 6). The inlet was angled at the centre of the composite end and a shallow channel across the mould at the inlet end facilitated the resin flow (Figs. 7 and 8). An outlet groove was used on the top and bottom mould halves to ease the resin outflow (Fig. 9). A seal groove was located circumferentially around the assembly part of the mould to ensure vacuum and prevent resin flow outside the mould. Four tapped jacking holes were used in the upper mould half and outside the seal groove to facilitate disassembly of the lower and upper mould parts after the RTM.

By alternating the clamping of the outlet pipes during the RTM, the resin flow in both mould halves (upper and lower) of the CFRP was ensured. Initially, 10 psi resin flow pressure was applied. Since the resin flowed from both outlets, both outlet pipes were clamped and a pressure of 40 psi was applied for 3-4 mins. Both outlet pipes were unclamped for a few seconds and clamped again afterwards. Finally, a 70 psi resin flow pressure was applied. This procedure ensured that there were no dry fibre patches left in the panel after the RTM.

Figure 6: Lower part of the mould.

Figure 7: Inlet and outlet configuration in the mould. Shallow channel across the inlet end facilitated the resin flow (Detail D), dimensions in mm.

Figure 8: Inlet detail, dimensions in mm.

Figure 9: Outlet groove on top and bottom mould halves to ease the resin outflow.

Spring steel plate specimens (EN 42) were cut to a width of 180 mm to fit in the mould. For high accuracy of perforation diameter, the steel part was perforated with a water-jet cutter. A PTFE circular rod of 6 mm nominal diameter was machined down to the various hole diameters using a lathe machine. Before RTM, steel substrates were sand-blasted and cleaned. Dry unidirectional fibres were placed in the mould to assemble the joint configuration (Fig. 10). After RTM was carried out, the co-infused panels were post-cured in an oven and cut by a water-jet into strips (specimens) with a nominal width of 30 mm. End tabs were not used.

Figure 10: Joint assembly in the mould, dry CFRP and perforated steel with and without PTFE inserts in the holes.

4.2 Tensile testing

Static tensile tests were performed. A 100 kN load cell Instron 6025 test machine was used. A fixed displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min was used for all the tests. The specimens were tested until final failure. The load and displacement reading were obtained from the machine load cell and extensometers, respectively. The experimentally tested configurations are summarised in Table 1.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Load-Displacement graphs

Load versus displacement graphs were obtained from the experimental tests. The displacements were calculated from an extensometer and from the test machine cross head displacement. However, the latter was significantly larger due to the compliance of the machine. Figure 11 compares the numerical predictions of the load versus displacement response with that obtained from the experiments (using extensometers for the displacement). The numerical and experimental results were in good agreement.

Test number	Abbreviation	Extensometer	Camera Type
1.1	REF	Yes	N/A
1.2	REF	Yes	N/A
1.3	REF	No	N/A
1.4	REF	No	PixeLINK
1.5	REF	No	High Speed
2.1	SH	Yes	N/A
2.2	SH	Yes	N/A
2.3	SH	No	High Speed
2.4	SH	No	N/A
2.5	SH	No	High Speed
3.1	LH	Yes	N/A
3.2	LH	Yes	N/A
3.3	LH	No	High Speed
3.4	LH	No	High Speed
3.5	LH	No	High Speed
4.1	SH with PTFE	No	High Speed
4.2	SH with PTFE	No	High Speed
4.3	SH with PTFE	Yes	N/A
4.4	SH with PTFE	Yes	N/A
5.1	LH with PTFE	No	N/A
5.2	LH with PTFE	No	N/A

Table 1: Summary of tested configurations, SH (Small Hole) and LH (Large Hole).

Figure 11: Comparison between the numerical predictions and measured experimental load-displacement response curves, comparing non-perforated (REF) and perforated (SH) steel joints.

According to Figure 11, the perforated joints exhibit higher stiffness throughout their loading comparing to the reference joints. The linear behaviour of the load-displacement curves for the perforated joints indicates a constant joint stiffness up to the failure point, where the joints failed catastrophically.

By contrast, non-perforated joints failed prematurely at the butt end and a crack propagated away from there to give failure of the first lap (corresponding to the step of the load-displacement curve; Fig. 11). After initial failure, the single intact lap withstood a further increased load until final failure occurred. The red solid line of Figure 11 shows the numerical response of an ideal non-defected reference specimen. However, during the experiments, even a small defect in one of the overlaps led to crack initiation/propagation and failure of one of the laps in an early loading stage. This defect was implemented in the numerical model (blue solid line) and it shows a very good agreement with the experimental curve (blue dashed line).

5.2 Maximum load comparison

Figure 12 summarises the measured maximum loads for all the experimental tests. The average maximum load obtained from the specimens for each test is given. Test 2.4 was not included in the calculation of the average maximum load of Test 2, as it was considered that the specimen failed prematurely, probably due to defects introduced during manufacturing.

As expected from the results of previous work on perforated steel to GFRP joints [2, 3, 8], the perforated joints have a significantly higher strength than the non-perforated joints. The average maximum load for the reference joint configurations was 17.7 kN, while in the perforated configurations the average maximum load was 47.6 kN, 44.9 kN and 48.7 kN for Test 2 (SH), Test 3 (LH) and Test 4 (SH with PTFE), respectively. Compared to non-perforated joints, perforated joints (SH with PTFE) showed a 175% increase of joint strength and without any premature joint failure.

The difference in the average maximum load for perforated joints with and without PTFE in the SH specimens was negligible. Thus, the hypothesis that the resin/fibres in the holes can produce mechanical interlocking and increase the joint strength was not correct. It is presumed that the dominant factor which contributed to the significantly higher strength of the perforated joints, comparing to the non-perforated ones, is the transitional zone of stiffness. The LH specimens without PTFE showed higher strength comparing to the LH with PTFE specimens. However, only two LH with PTFE specimens were tested and there was a large difference in the maximum load results between them. Thus, in the present study, there are not sufficient data to evaluate the mechanical interlocking hypothesis for the LH specimens.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A numerical and experimental investigation of CFRP to perforated steel joints has been presented. Compared to non-perforated joints, perforated joints showed a 175% increase of joint strength, a linear response, larger stiffness and failed catastrophically. The factor that contributed to the significantly higher strength of the perforated joints was the transitional zone of stiffness that the perforated joints offer. The mechanical interlocking that the resin/fibres in the holes produce offers no additional increase of the joint strength in the SH specimens.

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Figure 12: Comparison of maximum load between non-perforated and perforated steel joints.

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